

Effectiveness of Low Dose D-Penicillamine Therapy in Neurologic Wilson Disease - A Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract

Background: Wilson disease is an inherited disorder of copper metabolism that mostly manifests as hepatic and neurologic symptoms. Chelation therapy specially penicillamine is given as first line treatment in children with symptomatic Neurologic Wilson disease. **Objective:** Objective of the study was to assess the safety & the clinical outcome of treatment with low dose penicillamine in Neurologic Wilson disease. **Methods:** A longitudinal observational study was conducted at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), Dhaka, a tertiary care Premier Postgraduate Medical Institution of Bangladesh. Thirty-nine (39) patients of Neurologic Wilson disease who fulfill the inclusion and exclusion criteria were evaluated at In-patient Department of Paediatric Neurology, during the period of January 2015 to December 2019. All study children were treated with low dose penicillamine (Cap Artamin 250 mg) rather with conventional dose penicillamine (Cap Artamin 500 mg or 20 mg/kg/day). Subsequent follow up examination was performed at 2 weeks, 1, 3 and 6 months. Follow up was done by global assessment scoring (GAS) and slit lamp examination to see the clinical improvement after treatment with low dose penicillamine therapy. **Results:** Total number of studied cases were 39. Mean age was 10.2 ± 3.1 year and male to female ratio was 2:1. Most of the patients (66.67%) were arrived from rural area and 20.51% children had history of consanguineous mating parents. Common presenting features were progressive deterioration of school performance (89.74%), gait disturbance (92.31%), dysarthria (92.31%) and dystonia (82.06%) of our studied children. Ophthalmological manifestations like KF ring (100%) found in all patients. Neuroimaging showed bilateral basal ganglia involvement in (63.63%) children followed by hyperintense signal changes (18.18%) and ventricular dilatation in (18.18%) of cases. Majority of the children (74.36%) were improved with low penicillamine therapy clinically and KF ring disappeared in (5.12%) cases after drug therapy on follow up. Commonest side effects were worsening of neurological symptoms in (25.64%) and rash & thrombocytopenia in (5.1%) cases after penicillamine therapy. **Conclusion:** About three-fourth children of studied Neurologic Wilson disease showed gradual improvement with low-dose penicillamine therapy. Moreover,

More Information

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one-fourth of cases experienced neurological deterioration, which was lower than previously used high dose penicillamine therapy. Therefore, low dose penicillamine may be beneficial as an initial therapy for Wilson disease with neurological manifestations.

Introduction

Wilson disease (WD) is an inherited autosomal recessive disorder of copper metabolism leading to hepatic damage and neurological disturbance of variable degree [1]. The defective gene, ATP7B, encodes a hepatic copper-transporting protein, which plays a key role in human copper metabolism [2,3]. It usually manifests within the first three decades with liver dysfunction, extrapyramidal, neuropsychiatric, or osseomuscular (i.e., skeletal or musculoskeletal) symptoms and has marked inter- and intrafamilial clinical heterogeneity [4,5]

WD is a rare with an estimated prevalence of symptomatic disease of 1 in ~30,000 with a heterozygous ATP7B mutation carrier frequency of 1:90 (almost 1% of a population). Mutations in ATP7B result in impaired biliary copper excretion with consecutive copper overload primarily in the liver and later in the brain causing hepatic and neuro-psychiatric symptoms. Clinical manifestations are related to copper accumulation predominantly in the liver and brain. Hepatic disease are ranging from mild hepatitis to acute liver failure or cirrhosis and/or neurological symptoms are dysarthria, dystonia, tremor, and psychiatric disturbances [5,6]. Mixed presentations occur frequently. Early recognition of Wilson disease can be done by means of clinical, biochemical or genetic examination.

Untreated Wilson disease is fatal [7]. Chelation therapy is usually given as first line treatment in symptomatic Wilson disease. Wilson disease can be treated successfully with pharmacologic agents. Two groups of drugs are currently used: chelating agents such as D-penicillamine, tetrathiomolybdate, and trientine which increase urinary copper excretion, and zinc salts, which inhibit copper absorption in the digestive tract. In the majority of cases, treatment with drugs that induce a negative copper balance (usually chelators or zinc salts) leads to improvements in liver function and neurologic signs.

The mechanisms of action lead to a negative copper balance, stopping pathologic accumulation of copper in the various body tissues and clearing affected organs of copper overload. Due to a lack of prospective clinical trials, the use of drugs depends mainly on center experience and the accessibility in different countries or regions.

In spite of adequate treatment some neurologic deficits may persist and further neurologic deterioration may be observed after treatment initiation with chelating agents specially by penicillamine with conventional

dose. Such patients may require additional treatment to alleviate neurologic symptoms but most of the time very difficult to treat this case.

Treatment with D-penicillamine for neurologic WD is a long-term unresolved problem due to its reported side-effects and potential initial worsening of neurological manifestations. The patients who deteriorated on penicillamine therapy are a great challenge and the safety as well as efficacy of alternative drugs including trientine needs to be explored. That's why our aim was to observe the efficacy and outcome of treatment of Neurologic Wilson disease with low dose penicillamine therapy.

Materials and Methods

A longitudinal observational study was conducted at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), Dhaka, a tertiary care premier Postgraduate Medical Institution of Bangladesh.

Thirty-nine (39) patients of Neurologic Wilson disease were evaluated at In-patient department of Paediatric neurology, BSMMU during the period of January 2015 to December 2019. Diagnosis of Neurologic Wilson disease was based on the characteristic clinical features along with biochemical & neuro-imaging findings and ophthalmologic findings.

All patients with Neurologic Wilson disease who treated with low dose penicillamine (Cap Artamin 250 mg, irrespective age and weight) and/or with usual dose of zinc (25 mg twice daily in up to 6 years, 25 mg thrice daily in 6-15 years and 50 mg twice daily in 16 years and above) were included in this study. Children who treated with conventional dose penicillamine (Cap Artamin 500 mg or 20 mg/kg/day) or treated with other anticopper drugs were excluded from this study. Clinical assessment was performed by global assessment scoring (GAS) and slit lamp examination to see the clinical improvement after treatment with low dose penicillamine therapy. Biochemical evaluation was done by 24 hours' urinary copper, complete blood count, liver, and renal function tests. Follow up examinations was performed at 2 weeks, 1, 3 and 6 months of penicillamine therapy. Those who deteriorated or developed any adverse effects with low penicillamine therapy, only zinc was continued as maintenance therapy.

Statistical analysis

A descriptive statistics analysis was done using IBM SPSS statistics (version 22.0, 2013; Armonk, NY: IBM Corp) for data analysis. The data were compared using

Chi-square test or Fischer’s exact test, with $P < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Ethical permission was taken from the Institutional Review Board of BSMMU and informed written consent was taken from all parents of the participants.

Results

Total number of studied children was 39. Mean age was 10.2 ± 3.1 year and male to female ratio was 2:1. Most of the patients (66.67%) were arrived rural area of Bangladesh and 20.51% children had history of consanguineous mating parents. Progressive deterioration of school performance (89.74%), gait disturbance (92.31%), dysarthria (92.31%) and dystonia (82.06%) were the main presenting features of our studied children. Ophthalmological manifestations like KF ring (100%) found in all patients. Neuroimaging study showed bilateral basal ganglia involvement in (63.63%) children followed by hyperintense signal changes (18.18%) and ventricular dilatation in (18.18%) of cases.

Majority of the children (74.36%) were improved with penicillamine therapy. Commonest side effects were worsening of neurological symptoms in (25.64%) and rash & thrombocytopenia in (5.1%) cases after penicillamine therapy. KF ring disappeared in (5.12%) cases after therapy in follow up.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of studied cases (n=39)

Characteristics	Number of patients	Percentage
Age(yr):		
5-10	6	15.38%
11-15	31	79.49%
16-20	2	5.13%
Sex:		
Male	26	66.67%

Female	13	33.33%
Consanguinity:		
Consanguineous	8	20.51%
Non-consanguineous	31	79.49%
Affected sibs:		
Sibs affected	8	20.51%
Sibs not affected	31	79.49%

Table 1 showed that more than three fourth (79.49%) patients belonged to age 11-15 years. Mean age was 10.2 ± 3.1 year. More than two third (66.67%) children were male and about one third children (33.33%) were female. Male to female ratio was 2:1. About 20.51% patients came from consanguineous mating family and history of sibs affected in 20.51% children.

Table 2: Distribution of Neurologic manifestations in studied cases(n=39)

Symptoms	Number of patients	Percentage
Deterioration of school Performance	35	89.74%
Gait disturbance	36	92.31%
Dysarthria	36	92.31%
Dystonia	32	82.06%
Drooling of saliva	8	20.50%
Chorea/Athetosis	10	25.64%
Tremor	1	2.56%
Seizure	1	2.56%

Table 2 showed progressive deterioration of school performance occurred in 89.74% children followed by gait disturbance in 92.31%, dysarthria in 92.31%, dystonia in 82.06%, Choreaathetosis in 25.64% and drooling in 20.50% cases.

Figure 1: Distribution of neurologic manifestations in studied cases (n=39)

Table 3: Distribution of Psychiatric manifestations in studied cases (n=39)

Neuropsychiatric manifestations	Number of patients	Percentage
Change in behavior	25	64.10%
Depression	11	28.21%
Dysphasia	11	28.21%
Mania	27	69.23%
Postural abnormality	16	41.03%
Loss of memory	7	17.95%

Table 3 Showed psychiatric manifestations, such as behavior change found in 64.10% children followed by depression in 28.21%, dysphasia in 28.21% and mania in 69.23% and loss of memory in 17.95% cases.

Table 4: Distribution of ophthalmological findings in studied cases (n=39)

Ophthalmological Evaluation	Features	Number	Percentage
	Normal	0	0
	Abnormal : K F Ring (38), Sunflower cataract(1)	39	100%

Table 4. Abnormal ophthalmological findings (K F ring, Sunflower cataract) found in 100% of cases of neurologic Wilson diseases.

Table 5: Distribution of investigations of studied cases (n=39)

Investigations	Number of patients	Percentage
Low serum ceruloplasmin level	36	92.31%
High 24 hours urinary copper level	31	79.49%
After D-penicillamine high urinary copper level	37	94.87%
Low Hb%	6	15.38%
Abnormal USG of KUB: Left renal calculi	1	2.56%

Abnormal USG of HBS: Coarse hepatic parenchymal (11/28.20 %), Splenomegaly (5/12.82%)	16	41.03%
Abnormal MRI of brain	33	84.61%
Endoscopy of upper GIT: Esophageal varices	2	5.13%

Table 5 showed low serum ceruloplasmin level in 92.31%, high urinary copper level in 79.49%, Abnormal USG of HBS in 41.03%, Abnormal MRI of brain in 84.61% and Esophageal varices in endoscopy of upper GIT 5.13% cases.

Table 6: Distribution of Neuroimaging findings(MRI) in studied cases (n=33)

MRI of brain	Number of patients	Percentage
Bilateral basal ganglia involvement	21	63.63%
Hyperintense signal changes in brain	6	18.18%
Ventricular dilatation	6	18.18%

Table 6 showed MRI of brain showed bilateral basal ganglia involvement in 63.63% children followed by hyperintense signal changes 18.18% and ventricular dilatation in 18.18% of cases.

Table 7: Distribution of drug treatment in studied cases(n=39)

Treatment	Number of patients	Percentage
Low dose D-penicillamine (250mg) with Zinc (25 mg TDS)	35	89.74%
Low dose D-penicillamine (250mg) only	4	10.26%

Table 7 showed drug treatment in studied cases. Here, low dose D-penicillamine with Zinc was given in 89.74% cases and only low dose D-penicillamine therapy given in 10.26% of cases.

Table 8: Distribution of Side effects of D-penicillamine in studied cases (n=39)

Side effects of D-penicillamine	Number of patients	Percentage
Worsening of neurological symptoms	10	25.64%
Skin rash	2	5.12%
Thrombocytopenia	2	5.12%
Impaired liver function	1	2.56%

Table 8 showed worsening of neurological symptoms in 25.64%, skin rash in 5.12%, thrombocytopenia in 5.12%, and impaired liver function in 2.56% cases.

Table 9: Follow up of studied cases with D-penicillamine therapy(n=39)

Follow up	Number of patients	Percentage
Disappearance of KF ring		
Disappeared	2	5.13%
Not disappeared	37	94.87%
Clinical Improvement		
Improved	29	74.36%
Not improved	10	25.64%

Table 9 showed follow up of cases taking D-penicillamine therapy. Here disappearance of KF ring occurred in 5.13% and clinical improvement occurred in 74.36% cases.

Table 10 Follow up of studied cases after 6 months by gas (n=39)

Follow up at 6 months	Mean Gas Score ± Sd		P Value
	Before treatment	After treatment	
Clinically improved (n=29)	13.86 ± 2.21	5.34 ± 0.97	0.001
Clinically not improved (n=10)	20.70 ± 3.16	18.80 ± 2.20	0.137

Table 10 showed follow up of cases taking D-penicillamine therapy. P value was significant (P<0.001) in clinically improved group (Paired t-test).

Discussion

This longitudinal observational study was conducted at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), Dhaka. Thirty-nine (39) patients of Neurologic Wilson disease were evaluated at pediatric

neurology department during the period of January 2015 to December 2019. Follow up was done after treatment with low dose penicillamine (250mg) therapy and usual dose zinc sulfate as initial therapy followed by a maintenance therapy of zinc sulfate alone or in combination with D-penicillamine to manage WD effectively and safely.

Mean age was 10.2 ± 3.1 year and male to female ratio was 2:1. In another study [13] in 2014, median age was found 13 (4–41) years. Current study also showed, among 39 patients (20.51%) of them had history of consanguineous mating parents.

In this study, progressive deterioration of school performance (89.74%), gait disturbance (92.31%), dysarthria (92.31%) and dystonia (82.06%) were found. In a previous study [12] the neurological manifestations of 21 patients at the time of diagnosis were dysarthria (78%), tremor (65%), drooling (58%), dystonia (55%), incoordination (45%), hypokinetic speech (42%), dysphagia (35%), myoclonus (30%), spasticity (15%) and psychiatric symptoms (10%), which was consistent with the current study.

As in this study, majority of the patients with neurological Wilson disease, KF (Kayser-Fleischer) ring found in (100%) of patient. The presence of K-F rings was observed in (53.8%) of these patients [12] previously which is lower than the current study.

Neuroimaging study showed bilateral basal ganglia involvement in (63.63%) children followed by hyper intense signal changes (18.18%) and ventricular dilatation in (18.18%) of cases. In previous study [12] MRI or CT findings of the brain were abnormal in all symptomatic patients. The most frequently observed was increased density on CT and hyper intensity on T2 MRI in the region of the basal ganglia.

Majority of the children (74.36%) were improved with low dose penicillamine therapy in our study and P value was significant (P<0.001) in between clinically improved group and non-improved group. In a study¹¹ in 2015 results indicate a success rate for combination therapies of approximately (60%), which was much lower than expected. It was found to have strong evidence indicating that hepatic patients do not respond well to combination therapies, with a reported effectiveness rate of (47.1%) versus (78.6%) for patients with neurological manifestations. That figure is significantly less than those reported for DPA monotherapy [9] (73.7%), for TETA monotherapy [15] (82.6%), and for zinc monotherapy [16] (71.6%). KF ring disappeared in (5.13%) cases after therapy in follow up. In this study it was found that the commonest side effects were worsening of neurological symptoms, rash and thrombocytopenia after penicillamine therapy. D-penicillamine is a controversial treatment for neurologic WD due to its reported side-effects and potential initial worsening of neurological

manifestations. The patients who deteriorated on penicillamine are a great challenge and the safety and efficacy of alternative drugs including trientine needs to be explored. For this reason, in this study low dose D-penicillamine therapy was given instead of high conventional dose penicillamine therapy to evaluate the frequency and severity of worsening neurological symptoms.

Previous study reported [17] that (31.3%) patients treated with D-penicillamine had severe side-effects, including neurological worsening, pancytopenia, nephrotoxicity, polyneuropathy, optic neuritis and polymyositis. Of these patients who worsen, (50%) never recover from worsening condition.

Another study [10] of 27 patients with neurologic WD which was a retrospective study showed, 13 had shown initial deterioration usually within 2–6 weeks of penicillamine therapy. 6 of these 13 patients who deteriorated never improved to baseline even after discontinuation of penicillamine.

Medici V et al. showed [14] initial neurological deterioration was observed in as high as (75%) of patients following penicillamine therapy whereas none deteriorated following zinc. In our study it was found that the commonest side effects were worsening of neurological symptoms found in 25.64% cases which was much lower than Medici V et al study.

In terms of safety, the studies we reviewed reported a (35.8%) pooled adverse effect for all patients receiving some type of combination therapy (41.7%) for hepatic patients and (26.3%) for patients with neurological presentations [11].

In view of non-availability and high cost of trientine and other alternate drug as well as improvement in (74.35%) of Neurologic Wilson diseases following low dose penicillamine, patients may be started with Low dose penicillamine which should be escalated slowly with close monitoring till an alternative safe drug is available, Worsening of neurological symptoms in (25.64%) which was much lower than other study where high conventional dose of penicillamine used. In our study about majority of cases of Neurologic Wilson diseases (74.35%) were improved with low dose penicillamine therapy.

Conclusion

In our study about three fourth cases of Neurologic Wilson diseases were improved with low dose penicillamine therapy. One fourth cases of Neurologic Wilson diseases were deteriorated with this therapy that was lower compared to previously reported high dose therapy.

Therefore, low dose penicillamine may be beneficial as an initial therapy for Wilson disease with neurological presentation.

Limitation

The data was not so large and data collected from single point source and so further larger multi-centered study should be done.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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Author Contributions

Conceive and study design, data collection and data analysis: Prof. Dr. Gopen Kumar Kundu.

Clinical Help: Dr Rumana Islam, Dr sharmina Afrin Sheemu

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